

**IN THE WORKS OF NIZAM AL-DIN SHAMI DURING THE ERA OF AMIR
TIMUR AND THE TIMURIDS DYNASTY****Allayorova Sevinch Erkinovna****Karshi State University Faculty of History**

Annotation: The broad opportunities provided by independence facilitated a comprehensive study of the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period. The great achievements and the intellectual contributions made by them in the social-economic life and in the field of science during their lifetime undoubtedly play a crucial role in passing down their legacy to future generations

Key words: Amir Timur, Timurids, dynasty, history, Zafarnama, Hafizu Abru, Middle Ages, sources, historian.

Introduction: It is well-known that the Timurid era elevated the field of science to a high level because Sahibqiron and his descendants paid serious attention to the historical science. During this period, not only did they influence the history science on a global scale, but they also nurtured prominent historians throughout the entire Eastern world. Among them, scholars like Ghiyath al-Din Ali, Nizam al-Din Shami, Hafizi Abru, Mu'in al-Din Natanz, Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi, Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi, Mirkhond, and Khwandamir stand out. These scholars lived during the Timurid era and left behind invaluable works that shed light on the activities of the Timurid rulers.

One such historian is Nizam al-Din Shami. His original name was Ali ibn Muhammad[1], but in the works of some historians, he is known by names like Nizam al-Din Shambi or Mawlawi Nizam al-Din Shambi. While specific details about his birth year are not available, he passed away around 1404-1409. The historian Hafizi Abru narrates the events of the year 1412 and portrays them as an unfortunate incident. He refers to the deceased as a prominent figure. Hafizi Abru was not only a historian but also active as a translator, as indicated by historical records. Esteemed Orientalist scholars Hussein Nakhichevani and Donish Pajuhlar Shami have brought attention to certain details related to his scholarly activities. According to their accounts, Mawlawi Nizam al-Din Shami was famous under the name Nizam Tabrizi and, based on the assignment of Sheikh Uwais I (1356-1374), translated the work "Suluk al-Muttafi Uwon al-Atba" ("The Gardens of Discipleship in the Paths of Mystical Knowledge") by Muhammad ibn Abdullah ibn Zafar Makki Andalusi from Arabic to Persian. Likewise, Hafizi Abru also

produced another work, a brief translation of the life and teachings of Prophet Muhammad and the Twelve Imams, which he dedicated to Nizam ul-Vaiz, known by the name of Nizom[2].

The information about the 1412 events and Hafizi Abru's portrayal of himself in the "Zafarnama" is briefly discussed in a historical context. Furthermore, Donish Pajuh emphasizes that Nizam al-Vaiz was a well-known scholar, originally named Ali ibn Muhammad. His frequent use of the name Nizom in his works contributed to his fame. Donish Pajuh points out that Muhammad, known as Nizom ul-Vaiz, also translated an Arabic work into Persian, and he was famous during his time.

Shami describes his encounters and discussions with Sahibqiron in the "Zafarnama" and provides historical details about the writing of this work. Mawlawi Nizam al-Din, born around 1393, wrote about the events of August 1393 when Amir Timur's forces captured Baghdad. He mentions his personal experiences, including being the first to leave the city and his subsequent conversation with Sahibqiron. Amir Timur's later encounters with the scholar are described in the pages of the "Zafarnama" detailing the events of the year 1400. In October of that year, Amir Timur conquered the city of Aleppo in Syria. According to the author, during his journey to the Hijaz, when he was on a pilgrimage, the city guards detained him, accused him of disturbance, and put him in a building outside the city walls. From this place, he witnessed the capture of the city.

Hafizi Abru, the historian of the Timurid era, emphasizes that after the battle, when Jalol-us-Islam, an Amir named Nizomiddin Shomi, came to the presence of Sahibqiron, he was received with honor and kindness. The author suggests that Nizomiddin Shomi gained the favor and trust of Sahibqiron. The historian highlights the events that unfolded immediately after the conquest of the city, portraying Nizomiddin Shomi as a respected figure in the eyes of Sahibqiron.

Nizomiddin Shomi is credited with translating several works, and he is particularly renowned for translating the "Zafarnama." Sahibqiron praised him for his speedy completion of the work. The historian notes that Nizomiddin Shomi gained the attention and respect of Sahibqiron through his writing. It is suggested that Nizomiddin Shomi quickly became an advisor to Sahibqiron, gaining his trust and becoming a valuable member of his court.

The historical significance of Nizomiddin Shomi's translation of the "Zafarnama" is underlined, and the work is described as an easily understandable, straightforward, eloquent, and simultaneously informative piece of writing. It is emphasized that the work was presented in a manner accessible to the general public and was appreciated for its clarity and educational value. "Afterward, we recognized a high potential for a comprehensive study of the history of the

Timurid era, focusing on Amir Timur and the period of the Timurids. The significant efforts and contributions made by these rulers in socio-economic life, as well as in the fields of knowledge and science during their reign, are undoubtedly essential in evaluating the role and significance of these historians in history[3].

It is acknowledged that during the Timurid era, there was a significant advancement in the realm of knowledge due to the rulers and their descendants showing serious attention to historical matters. This period witnessed the emergence of distinguished historians renowned not only for documenting the history of the state but also gaining fame throughout the Eastern world. Among them were notable figures such as Ghiyath al-Din Ali, Nizam al-Din Shami, Hofizi Abru, Mu'in al-Din Natanz, Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi, Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi, Mirkhond, and Khondamir, among others. These scholars lived during the Timurid era, and their works actively contributed to the intellectual and cultural legacy of the period. Here, we provide brief information about the lives and scholarly contributions of some of these historians. Nizam al-Din Shami, originally known as Ali ibn Muhammad, is a prominent figure mentioned in the works of other historians such as Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi, Abd al-Razzaq Samarqandi, Khondamir, and others. Although precise information about the year of his birth is not available, he is believed to have passed away between 1404 and 1409[5].

Subsequently, Nizomiddin Shomiy provides further clarification about the stringent requirements placed on the scholars by Sohibqiron. Sohibqiron said to him, 'In the books that have been written in this style and have been adorned with metaphors and embellishments, the intended purposes are often lost. If one of those who adhere to the principles of language and law understands its meaning, they will comprehend its essence. However, the remaining part, even the sentence structure, perhaps the language, may not be as beneficial as intended.'

Nizomiddin Shomiy emphasizes that Sohibqiron's benefit cannot be equal for everyone because understanding the content, reaching the goal requires effort. Therefore, adhering to Sohibqiron's responsible demand, the scholar states, 'I made such a prayer when preparing for the ceremony: If the laws are established, I will go on this path with this bond. I will try to leave according to his will until my power is exhausted, and I will not consider this service as an honor.' As observed, Amir Timur acted to promote the creation of historical works with a specific purpose, considering the narrative style for history, present, and future. Therefore, Shomiy Sohibqiron actively worked to meet the requirements of Sohibqiron." After the mentioned campaign, Nizomiddin Shomiy, as the chief historian of the great ruler, Amir Timur, continued to support him in all subsequent military campaigns. He described the conquest of the Birtis fortress in Georgia in the month of Muharram of the year 806 (July-August 1403). Shomiy

recounts that during one of the campaigns, Amir Timur gathered a congregation on the occasion of the Eid al-Fitr, delivered a sermon, and then performed the Eid prayer. This event is vividly described by the famous historian Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi, who stated that "His Majesty (Amir Timur) left swiftly, returned after a short time, and celebrated Eid on the plain of Oghlaq Suyidin Baloravadqa. They stayed there for several days, passing Ramadan, and then performed the Eid prayer. On Saturday, the day of Eid, which was the twelfth day of the month of April 1404, Mavlono Nizomuddin Shibliqim, a well-known scholar, delivered a sermon after the Eid prayer. After the prayer, they engaged in discussions, conducted invocations, and expressed gratitude to the virtuous present in the assembly."

According to the academician Bori Boy Ahmedov, "Zafarnama" exists in two versions. The first was completed by Nizomiddin Shomiy in the spring of 1404, presenting it to Amir Timur during his return journey from Ojarbayjan to Samarkand. The manuscript is not named, and the second version is dedicated to Mirzo Umar, the grandson of Mironshoh, during the period when Amir Timur was in Qoraboqda on March 26, 1404, presenting him the "Halokukhon Takhti" ("The Throne of Destruction"). The second version differs from the first, with some stylistic modifications and the addition of a small appendix (Zayl).

Nizomiddin Shomiy created "Zafarnama" based on various sources, including Amir Timur's letters written by Uyghur scribes in the "Tarikhi Khoni" ("History of the Khan") style. The historian utilized the original manuscripts and documents to enhance the value of his work. Today, copies of "Zafarnama" are preserved in various libraries worldwide, including Armenia (Yerevan), and notable translations into Russian and French were published [6].

During the years of independence, our scholars' efforts led to the translation of "Zafarnama" into the Uzbek language in 1996. The translation was carried out by Yunusjon Hakimjonov, with additional work by Asomiddin Urinboyev, Habibullo Karomatov, Omonullo Buriyev, and Muborak Fozilova.

In conclusion, Nizomiddin Shomiy and his work "Zafarnama" have great significance, shedding light on the history of Amir Timur's campaigns and providing valuable insights into the political and social history of Uzbekistan and neighboring regions during the late 14th and early 15th centuries. His work gained even more importance during subsequent centuries when historians like Sharaf al-Din Ali Yazdi referred to it, confirming its authenticity.

The literature used in the response includes the following sources:

1. Azamat Ziyov. History of Uzbek Identity. - T.: "Sharq", 2001. P. 203.

2. Ahmedov B. Sources of Uzbekistan's History. 2nd edition. - T., "Oqituvchi", 2001. P. 165-166.

3. Azamat Ziyoy. Cited work. - T.: "Sharq", 2001. P. 203.

4. Nizomiddin Shomiy. "Zafarnoma" (The Book of Victory). Translation by Yu. Hakimjonov. Prepared for publication and responsible editor A. Urinboev. – Tashkent: "O'zbekiston", 1996. P. 4.

5. Ahmedov B. Sources of Uzbekistan's History. – Tashkent: "Oqituvchi", 2001. P. 166.

6. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi. "Zafarnoma" (The Book of Victory). Editors: Ashraf Ahmad and Khaydarbek Bobobekov. Responsible editor: Barnobek Eshpulatov. Tashkent, 1997, 289 pages. Page 283.